

Quanti Farm

COST & BENEFIT CALCULATORS

quantifarm.eu

FACTSHEET #3

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WHAT IS IT?

The **Cost & Benefit Calculators** tool is an interactive component of the QuantiFarm Toolkit that supports the economic assessment of Digital Agriculture Technology Solutions (DATSs).

It enables users to estimate the financial implications of adopting DATSs in both crop and livestock farming systems, using farm-specific inputs and harmonised calculation modules. By translating technical impacts into economic indicators such as investment costs, operational savings, Return on Investment (ROI), and Net Benefit, the tool provides a clear and realistic view of the economic feasibility of digital technologies across their lifecycle.

KEY OBJECTIVES

To **support evidence-based decision-making** on the adoption of Digital Agriculture Technology Solutions

To **estimate and compare the economic costs and benefits** of DATSs in crop and livestock farming systems

To **translate farm-level data into comparable economic indicators**, including ROI and Net Benefit

To **reduce uncertainty and investment risk** associated with digital technology uptake

To **contribute to a better understanding of the economic performance of DATSs** across diverse farming contexts

MAIN FEATURES

Structured DATS search and selection

Users can filter DATSs by farming system, crop or livestock type, DATS category, and farming practice.

Farm-specific data input

Users enter their own operational data (e.g., area, yields, input costs, animal numbers, production levels).

DATS evaluation with descriptive information

Each DATS includes details such as purpose, provider, platform, and cost information to support informed selection.

Modular calculation engine

Dedicated calculator modules estimate:

- ◇ Investment and operational costs
- ◇ Yield or productivity increases
- ◇ Input reductions (e.g., fertiliser, water, feed, labour, energy)
- ◇ Revenue increases and cost savings

Automated system analysis

Results are calculated dynamically based on user inputs and farming system-specific formulas.

Clear presentation of results

Outputs include consolidated results with ROI, net benefit, total costs, and total savings, displayed in an intuitive dashboard.

Applicability to both crop and livestock systems

Tailored calculator modules reflect the specific economics of different farming contexts.

MAIN FEATURES

WHO IS IT FOR?

Farmers and farm managers

seeking to evaluate whether a DATS is economically viable for their farm

Advisers, consultants, and advisory services

supporting investment and digitalisation decisions

Digital Innovation Hubs and technology promoters

demonstrating the economic value of DATSs

Policymakers and other stakeholders

interested in understanding farm-level economic impacts and the scalability of digital solutions

Cost & Benefit Calculators Access

The QuantiFarm Cost & Benefit Calculators is available online through the project's official platform and continuously updated based on user feedback and new test results.

Contact

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